
Confidence Herding Under Market Distress

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Received: 2022-09-17

Accepted: 2022-10-05

Published online: 2022-10-22

Abstract

This paper investigates the role of government ownership in investor herding during volatile market conditions. The researcher documents significant confidence herding (attributed to government ownership) during market distress. To be specific, the researcher examined investor reactions during extreme market conditions, using daily data from the Chinese stock market from 1991 to 2016. The researcher shows that investors exhibit significant herd behavior in the Chinese market during extreme (high/low) market conditions, suggesting the existence of investor irrationality during such conditions. In addition, the magnitude of investor herding is greater in extremely high market conditions than extremely low market conditions. Most importantly, investors herd in high-state-owned stocks during extremely low market conditions. In contrast, investors do not exhibit significant herding in high-state-owned stocks during extremely high market conditions. The evidence implies that government ownership garners investor confidence during market distress.

Keywords: Herding, Government Ownership, China, Stock Market, Investor Behavior, Market Distress.

1. Introduction

There have been heated debates in finance literature regarding the efficiency of government ownership. There are two broad views regarding the efficiency of government ownership: some argue for the efficient role (Faccio et al., 2006; Martin & Parker, 1995; Vernon-Wortzel & Wortzel, 1989) while others argue for the inefficient role (Bai et al., 2004; Boycko et al., 1996; La Porta et al., 2002). The extensive literature on government ownership largely focuses on its relationships with corporate governance and firm performance (e.g., Borisova et al., 2012; Tian & Estrin, 2008).

Despite this ongoing debate on its efficiency, evidence shows that government ownership garners investor confidence especially during crises since governments can provide financially distressed firms with external help (Beuselinck et al., 2017).

This confidence level reflects investors' perception of whether or not government ownership is associated with more safety of their invested portfolios in the market. For instance, investors can exhibit a higher level of confidence in state-owned enterprises than private-owned enterprises during crises, due to the fact that governments may not allow state-owned enterprises to fail. Therefore, the impact of government ownership on investor reactions would be especially prevalent during extreme market conditions.

As such, the paper examines how government ownership impacts investor herding during extreme market conditions. Daily data of the Chinese market were used from 1991 to 2016, where there is a sufficient presence of government ownership during the sample period. The research finds that government ownership plays a significant role in terms of influencing investor herd behavior.

This paper highlights the presence of herding in China's equity market, using the measure in Christie & Huang (1995), which is a cross-sectional measure of dispersion of stock returns. The results show that, either in an extreme low-state market (1% and 5% market distress days) or in an extreme high-state market (1% and 5% days with extreme returns), there are herd effects in China's equity market within all industries. Notably, the magnitude of herding during an extreme up market is about twice as much as that during an extreme down market, which potentially indicates that investors are more engaged with this type of behavioral bias when the market is up and the happiness from making money is spread around the market. This is consistent with the view in Huberman & Regev (2001b) that optimism is contagious and enthusiastic public attention can move the market.

Particularly, this paper shows that one of the channels causing herd behavior in China's equity market relates to an important set-up in this market, namely the state ownership. This is because the evidence shows that market returns significantly herd around state-owned companies compared with non-state-owned companies during both extreme up and down markets. In addition, the market herds around companies with a high state-ownership (taking at least 50% of the total ownership) when the market is low. This can probably be explained by the fact that investors prefer these state-owned companies during market distress, since they believe that state-owned companies are safer than other companies. However, whether herding around state-owned companies eventually brings benefits to investors are worth future investigation.

Moreover, an important set-up (i.e., state ownership) matters in China's equity market especially during extreme market conditions, which has broad implications for the regulators and governors in terms of reforming China's financial systems and economic structures. In particular, historically, state ownership plays a very important role in China's economic development and economic reform (Tong & Kunkel, 2022). However, herding within state ownership might indicate less market efficiency and this definitely should be taken into consideration for future market design and regulation.

This paper relates to several debates in literature. First, this paper contributes to the literature on government ownership (e.g., Beuselinck et al., 2017; Borisova et al., 2015) by identifying a significant role that it plays in influencing investor behavior in the stock market. Second, this paper adds to the debates regarding the efficiency of the Chinese stock market by presenting evidence of market inefficiency (herding) during extreme market conditions. Third, this paper contributes to the herding literature (e.g., Chang et al., 2000; Chiang & Zheng, 2010; Christie & Huang, 1995; Hirshleifer & Teoh, 2003) by showing that government ownership can alter investor herding especially during extreme market conditions. In addition, this paper has implications on the market-oriented economic reform in China, especially the reform of state-owned enterprises. This is because the results suggest that government ownership mitigates the market-level return volatility during extreme market conditions. Therefore, regulators and policy makers may have to consider the trade-off between the market inefficiency and the reduced volatility associated with government ownership.

2. Related Literature

Due to the large number of individual investors in the Chinese stock market, most of whom are unsophisticated investors, the collective investing decisions of the investors captured by the market, which are reflected in the stock prices, might be counter-productive from their initial intentions (Chong et al., 2017). The knowledge-demanding information released from financial reporting, changes of financial data in the market, and outside information (policy changes, company rating, etc.) also play a significant role in affecting investing behavior.

Individual investors may have an inability to read and understand intricate financial information and be unable to react to market information promptly. Since individual investors make up a large portion in this market, the accumulative trading behavior of the market could be biased, compared to those markets largely made up of relatively rational institutional investors. Therefore, the market efficiency is negatively affected in China by investor irrationality. This is aligned with the extensive literature which shows that emerging markets are less efficient than developed markets (Bekaert & Harvey, 2002; Bhattacharya et al., 2000; Griffin et al., 2010; Harvey, 1995; Rouwenhorst, 1999; van der Hart et al., 2003).

However, very limited research has been done to connect the different set-ups (e.g., government ownership) in China's stock market and the inadequately explained empirical outcomes (e.g., herding). Chong et al. (2017) examine the determinants of herd behavior in the Chinese market using the framework proposed by Chang et al. (2000). Chong et al. (2017) find evidence of herd behavior in the Chinese market and no significant difference in herd behavior between state-owned enterprises and non-state-owned enterprises.

However, to the best of researcher's knowledge, the literature remains silent on whether investors tend to herd around state-owned enterprises particularly during extreme market conditions when investor might exhibit different behavior. The measure of herd behavior in Christie & Huang (1995) focuses on examining herd behavior during extreme market conditions; whereas the measure in Chang et al. (2000) does not particularly focus on extreme market conditions.

As such, in this paper, using the framework, the researcher empirically investigates and identifies how government ownership affects herding in the Chinese market during extreme market conditions as proposed by Christie & Huang (1995). This will contribute to the understanding of how market-specific set-ups influence investor behavior and the underlying mechanisms in terms of when and why investor irrationality emerges.

2.1 Herd Effect in the Stock Markets

The word "herding" literally means the act of bringing animals in a group. When researchers consider this concept in the financial market, it means that a group of investors (e.g., institutions or individuals) trade in the same direction over a period of time (Nofsinger & Sias, 1999). There are papers published on this topic, but there still are some questions that need answering, particularly regarding the sensitivity of herding to some specific market set-ups, such as ownership structures.

2.1.1 Herding in the US Stock Market

Many questions have been investigated on herd behavior in the stock market in prior literature. Grinblatt et al. (1995) document two important elements of the US stock market: (1) mutual funds have a tendency to buy stocks based on their past returns (momentum); (2) mutual funds tend to buy and sell the same stocks at the same time (i.e., herd). Christie & Huang (1995) test herd behavior in the US equity market on both daily and monthly frequencies. Christie & Huang (1995) find no evidence of the presence of herd behavior in the US equity market during the periods of market distress. Nofsinger & Sias (1999) provide a model to test the herd behavior of individual investors and institutional investors. Sias (2004) argues that institutional investors trade based more on tendency to follow each other (i.e., herding) (lag trades) rather than based on the tendency to do momentum trading (lag returns). Nofsinger & Sias (1999) suggest that the impact of institutional herding on stock prices is greater than herding of individual investors.

2.1.2 Herding in China's Stock Market

Scholars researching multiple aspects of the Chinese market have reached different conclusions about the presence of herd behavior. Fu & Lin (2010) find that

there is no herding in China's equity market. Demirer & Kutan (2006) argue that herd formation does not exist in China's stock market in both Shanghai and Shenzhen.

However, Tan et al. (2008) conclude that there is evidence of herding within both Shanghai and Shenzhen and both A-share market and B-share market. Yao et al. (2014) show that herding strongly exists in China's B-share market and is especially prevalent during declining market conditions.

Research on the US market has come to the consensus that herd behavior does not exist, whereas in China's stock market, research has not reached a consensus. There is a debate on whether there is or is not a herd effect in China. Furthermore, prior literature focuses on the herd effect by looking at the stock market as a whole, which could be described as "collective effects". Yet very limited research looks at why herding exists or not exists specifically in China (Chong et al., 2017). The question has not yet been answered in terms of where investor herd and why investor herd around specific categories of stocks. The nature of the stocks or the companies (i.e., ownership structures) is not considered when testing herd behavior during extreme market conditions, while this is an important issue in terms of investors' preferences.

2.2 State-ownership and the Chinese Stock Market

In China's stock market, there are many state-owned companies listed within a wide range of business sectors, such as utility, energy, manufacturing, banking, and so forth (Ding & Suardi, 2019; Gul et al., 2010; Sun & Tong, 2003). Furthermore, individual investors are prevalent in China's stock market, which means individual investors play a significant role in this market. Individual investors are more likely to invest in state-owned companies in the stock market when they do not have sufficient knowledge to evaluate the messages or information (financial reporting, changing of stock prices, etc.) and make knowledge-based investing decisions. This is because the investment in these companies can be safer than private-owned companies given the implicit government guarantee (Borisova & Megginson, 2011; Brown & Dinç, 2011; Faccio et al., 2006). As a result, individual investors may simply invest in the companies they trust more; individual investors in China trust government-promoted industries because these industries are generally supported by a variety of policies, which makes investment in these companies less risky.

More empirical work needs to be done on emerging markets where, as the evidence suggests, one is likely to find a greater tendency to herd (Bikhchandani & Sharma, 2000). In China, investors may have different preferences on stocks based on their knowledge about enterprises' ownership structures, and thus government ownership makes a difference when examining investor herding in the China's stock market.

3. Hypothesis Development

Literature shows that government-owned businesses provide additional safety features compared to private-owned businesses (e.g., Borisova & Megginson, 2011; Brown & Dinç, 2011; Dinç, 2005). There are at least three reasons why investors should consider government ownership to be associated with more safety. First, government ownership provides firms with a higher level of ability for repayment. It is documented that government ownership is associated with an implicit government guarantee (Borisova & Megginson, 2011; Brown & Dinç, 2011; Faccio et al., 2006). One example can be that bondholders trust the implicit guarantee to repay debtholders, which reduces the cost of debt of government-owned firms (Borisova & Megginson, 2011). For the same reason, government ownership increases a company's ability to repay debt, benefiting shareholder interest.

Second, government ownership facilitates firms to access financial resources. For example, politically connected firms are more likely to benefit from a government bailout compared to non-connected firms (Faccio et al., 2006). In addition, government-owned banks are more willing to finance projects which are beneficial to the economic development than other banks (Dinç, 2005). Government-owned firms are also usually of economic and political importance (Borisova & Megginson, 2011).

Third, the intervention nature of government ownership reduces the risk for firms to fail (Brown & Dinç, 2011). Given the strategic importance of government ownership (e.g., utilities), governments will not allow these firms to go bankrupt (Borisova & Megginson, 2011). For example, using a sample of banks in twenty-one emerging markets the 1990s, Brown & Dinç (2011) document that no bank with more than 50% government ownership went bankrupt, while around 44% banks of the remaining sample were either acquired or nationalized.

Given these safety features of government ownership, investors thus have sufficient reasons to perceive government ownership as an indication of the safety of their investment. For instance, investors can exhibit a higher level of confidence in state-owned enterprises (Borisova & Megginson, 2011; Leland & Pyle, 1977; Perotti, 1995). The impact of government ownership on investor reactions would be especially prevalent during extreme market conditions (Christie & Huang, 1995; Hwang & Salmon, 2004; Raimundo Júnior et al., 2020). As such, the researcher examines a particular type of investor behavior, namely herding, during extreme market conditions applying a widely used model developed by Christie & Huang (1995).

Herding is widely used in literature as an indicator of market efficiency or inefficiency given the specific type of herding (Bikhchandani & Sharma, 2000; Nofsinger & Sias, 1999; Sias, 2004). For instance, the herding measure in Christie & Huang (1995) captures the irrationality of investors and inefficient asset prices.

Emerging markets are less efficient than the US market (Bekaert & Harvey, 2002; Bhattacharya et al., 2000; Griffin et al., 2010; Harvey, 1995; Rouwenhorst, 1999; van der Hart et al., 2003). One would expect that the Chinese market is less efficient than the US market, thus it should exhibit herding during extreme market conditions (H1).

However, investor reactions should be asymmetric during extreme market conditions. For instance, investors are expected to exhibit a higher level of herding during extremely high market conditions compared to extremely low market conditions (H2). This is because optimism is contagious and enthusiastic public attention can induce a permanence price rise (Huberman & Regev, 2001).

In contrast, conditioning on a high government ownership (more than 50%), investor reactions should be more significant during extremely low market conditions compared to extremely high market conditions. This is because investors are loss averse (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979; Tversky & Kahneman, 1992). For the purposes of seeking safety, investors should exhibit herd behavior in high-state-owned enterprises during extremely low market conditions, if they have a higher level of confidence in government ownership (H3).

Therefore, the researcher hypothesizes that (1) investors exhibit herd behavior in extreme market conditions in the Chinese market, (2) the magnitude of herding during extremely high market conditions is significantly larger compared to extremely low market conditions, and (3) investors exhibit a higher level of herding in government ownership during extremely low market conditions to seek safety.

4. Data

The researcher uses data from CSMAR (China Stock Market & Accounting Research Database), which is a database particularly devoted to China's financial markets. This database is widely used for studies on China's financial markets. The stock returns are daily data ranging from 1991 to 2016.¹ The ownership structure is calculated as the proportion of shares of a certain kind of ownership to all stock shares outstanding for a company. In this paper, state ownership is calculated as the proportion of stock shares that are owned by the state to all market shares outstanding for each company.

¹ The data range is limited by data availability. The data during the 2008 global financial crisis is not excluded from the sample as the methodology used in this paper will capture the herd behavior during that period of time as extreme market conditions.

5. Methodology

5.1 Identification of Herd Effects

There are a number of ways to identify the herd effect in the stock market in prior literature (Christie & Huang, 1995; Lakonishok, Shleifer, & Vishny, 1992; Nofsinger & Sias, 1999). For example, little evidence is found of herding in the US stock market by using both daily and monthly data of stock returns (Christie & Huang, 1995). This econometrical method became widely used to identify herding in the stock market. However, little effort is shown in prior literature to further investigate the structural herd effect within different categories of stocks and to determine whether ownership structures matter for herd behavior in the market. This paper adopts Christie & Huang's (1995) method and applies it to China's stock market, while taking into consideration the prevalence of state ownership. State ownership is a particularly important feature that distinguishes the Chinese market from the US market.

Christie & Huang's (1995) method is developed as follows. The dispersion of equity returns, S , is measured by the following equation:

$$S = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (r_i - \bar{r})^2}{n - 1}} \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

Regression model:

$$S_t = \alpha + \beta_1 D_t^L + \beta_2 D_t^U + \varepsilon_t \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

Where, $D_t^L = 1$, if the market return on day t lies in the extreme lower tail of the return distribution, and $D_t^L = 0$ otherwise; $D_t^U = 1$, if the market return on day t lies in the extreme upper tail of the return distribution, and $D_t^U = 0$ otherwise. The α coefficient denotes the average dispersion of the sample excluding the regions covered by the two dummy variables.

Dispersion, or the cross-sectional standard deviation of returns, is used to describe and indicate the existence of herding in the stock market, since when individual stock returns tend to exhibit lower dispersion, there is more consensus from the investors to trade in the same direction (herding) (Christie & Huang, 1995). In contrast, if the market is efficient, people are expected to trade in different directions (higher dispersion) due to the varied sensitivity to market movements. This observation is consistent with the rational market model.

5.2 State-ownership and Herd Effects

A very important aspect of this model is that the dispersion S_t is a within-group dispersion calculated with each group. In order to look into the herd effects with respect to different levels of state-ownership, stocks are sorted in terms of the year-average state-ownerships into four different groups: Group (Control) for companies with zero state-ownership, Group (Low) for companies with 0 to 25% state-ownership, Group (Mid) for companies with 25% (included) to 50% state-ownership, and Group (High) for companies with more than 50% (included) state-ownership. For the dummy variables D_t^L and D_t^U , the researcher calculates the equally weighted average stock returns for every trading day in each year within different groups.

Table 1 Summary Statistics

This table presents the summary statistics of the state ownership and the stock return dispersion between different groups.

Industry	Sorting	State Ownership					Dispersion				
		N	Mean	Std	Min	Max	Obs	Mean	Std	Min	Max
Finance (001)	Group 0 (Control)	36	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	5,398	3.48	1.52	0.00	11.59
	Group 1 (Low)	32	0.11	0.07	0.00	0.25	5,535	3.22	1.90	0.00	13.57
	Group 2 (Mid)	27	0.39	0.07	0.26	0.48	4,237	3.24	1.86	0.00	13.74
	Group 3 (High)	26	0.65	0.10	0.50	0.83	4,578	3.25	1.83	0.00	13.88
Utilities (002)	Group 0 (Control)	309	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	5,870	3.69	0.83	0.00	17.11
	Group 1 (Low)	136	0.09	0.07	0.00	0.25	5,338	3.54	1.25	0.00	13.35
	Group 2 (Mid)	98	0.39	0.07	0.25	0.50	5,858	3.59	1.10	0.00	9.50
	Group 3 (High)	107	0.62	0.07	0.50	0.82	5,911	3.66	1.03	0.00	12.07
Properties (003)	Group 0 (Control)	147	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	5,880	3.61	0.84	0.02	8.20
	Group 1 (Low)	88	0.11	0.08	0.00	0.25	5,748	3.58	1.05	0.00	12.23
	Group 2 (Mid)	67	0.36	0.06	0.26	0.49	5,833	3.53	1.24	0.00	10.90
	Group 3 (High)	69	0.61	0.07	0.50	0.75	6,037	3.51	1.14	0.00	13.22
Conglomerates (004)	Group 0 (Control)	69	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	5,965	3.55	1.17	0.00	10.04
	Group 1 (Low)	48	0.10	0.07	0.01	0.24	6,239	3.47	1.38	0.00	13.09
	Group 2 (Mid)	28	0.35	0.07	0.26	0.48	4,986	3.34	1.64	0.00	13.38
	Group 3 (High)	11	0.62	0.06	0.55	0.76	2,585	3.34	1.65	0.00	10.59
Industrials (005)	Group 0 (Control)	1,383	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	6,073	3.73	0.76	0.00	11.14
	Group 1 (Low)	621	0.09	0.07	0.00	0.25	5,768	3.67	0.82	0.00	9.81
	Group 2 (Mid)	454	0.38	0.06	0.25	0.50	6,028	3.65	0.83	0.00	15.48
	Group 3 (High)	421	0.61	0.07	0.50	0.92	5,941	3.68	0.77	0.01	7.91
Commerce (006)	Group 0 (Control)	117	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	5,740	3.56	1.11	0.00	9.87
	Group 1 (Low)	63	0.11	0.08	0.00	0.25	5,045	3.55	1.30	0.00	10.84
	Group 2 (Mid)	71	0.37	0.06	0.26	0.49	5,811	3.53	1.24	0.00	12.81
	Group 3 (High)	50	0.60	0.08	0.51	0.88	5,433	3.47	1.31	0.00	10.37

Therefore, it becomes possible to use the following regressions to identify herd effects in different groups of stocks with respect to state-ownership. Specifically, in (Equation 3, S_{igt} is the dispersion of returns of stocks in the above mentioned four groups (Group Control, Group Low, Group Mid, and Group High), with respect to state-ownership in different industries, where δ_i represents industry fixed effects and Group is a dummy variable, representing the level of state-ownership. In addition, in (Equation 4

both industry fixed effects (δ_i) and group fixed effects (θ_g) are controlled, and the cross terms capture the joint influence from both state-ownerships and market states.

$$S_{igt} = \alpha + \delta_i + \beta_1 D_t^L + \beta_2 D_t^U + \text{Group} + \varepsilon_t \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

$$S_{igt} = \alpha + \delta_i + \theta_g + \beta_1 D_t^L + \beta_2 D_t^U + \text{Group} + \beta_3 D_t^L \times \text{Group} + \beta_4 D_t^U \times \text{Group} + \varepsilon_t \quad (\text{Equation 4})$$

According to above analyses, this paper predicts investors in China prefer to herd around state-owned companies' stocks, and thus exhibit more significant herd behavior compared to that of private-owned companies' stocks, especially when the market is experiencing a downward trend (or under distress). In this paper, the market distress is described as times when the market is in extreme flux (such as the upper tail and lower tail of the stock return distribution).

6. Empirical Tests

6.1 Identification of Herd Effects

To be specific, the results in Table 2 show that in both the 1% criterion and the 5% criterion, there are herd effects in China's stock market within each industry from 1991 to 2016. For the 1% criterion, the overall market herding captured by β_1 is -0.1850 and -0.5908 by β_2 . Both coefficients are significant at the 1% level, which means when the stock market is in an extreme good or bad state; there is significant herding in the overall stock market.

Table 2 Herd Effect Identification among Industries

This table presents the results of the herd effect in China's stock market from 1991 to 2016. The dependent variables here are dispersions within six industries (finance, utilities, properties, conglomerates, industrials and commerce). Within all industries and in each individual industry, both the 1% criterion and the 5% criterion are tested in the regressions. β_1 captures the herd effect when the market is in an extreme low state and β_2 captures the herd effect when the market is in an extreme high state.

Industry	1 Percent Criterion			5 Percent Criterion		
	α	β_1	β_2	α	β_1	β_2
All industries	3.6685	-0.1850*** (-3.80)	-0.5908*** (-11.61)	3.7076	-0.2942*** (-14.06)	-0.6454*** (-30.93)
Finance 001	3.6143	-0.2640* (-1.70)	-0.4313*** (-2.69)	3.6485	-0.2852*** (-4.31)	-0.5408*** (-8.19)
Utilities 002	3.7129	-0.2244** (-2.24)	-0.5938*** (-5.70)	3.7530	-0.2868*** (-6.75)	-0.6802*** (-16.01)
Properties 003	3.6618	-0.2224** (-2.35)	-0.5631*** (-5.65)	3.7008	-0.2939*** (-7.28)	-0.6437*** (-15.97)
Conglomerates 004	3.6205	-0.08135 (-0.63)	-0.6632*** (-4.87)	3.6587	-0.2444*** (-4.30)	-0.6721*** (-11.94)
Industrials 005	3.7356	-0.07248 (-0.60)	-0.6147*** (-4.82)	3.7733	-0.2759*** (-5.24)	-0.6213*** (-11.91)
Commerce 006	3.6626	-0.2623** (-2.49)	-0.6653*** (-6.02)	3.7077	-0.3797*** (-8.48)	-0.7103*** (-15.80)

However, when the market is extremely low, there are no significant herd effects among conglomerates and industrials. Interestingly, for all other industries and the overall market, the coefficients of β_2 are as much as twice that of β_1 . This result indicates that the magnitude of herd effects in an extreme good-state market is two times as big as that in an extreme bad-state market. This makes sense because investors should be happier to herd around a good-state market than a bad-state market, which leads to a higher magnitude of herding when the market situation is good.

In addition, for the 5% criterion in this table, the herd effects are 1%-level significant among all industries and the overall market. Still, the magnitude of herding in an extreme good-state market is approximately twice that of herding in an extreme bad-state market. The average dispersion (α) for each industry is very similar. This similarity of average dispersion across industries indicates that the herd effect is not an industry-specific phenomenon, but rather, that there might be other driving factors contributing to herd effects among the market, which will be discussed later.

Notably, the results in Table 2 are not only different from the comparable results in the US market but also different from prior studies on China's market. Christie & Huang (1995) find that both the coefficients β_1 and β_2 are significantly positive in the US market, which indicates there are no herd effects in the US. Using the same method but with a much smaller sample, Demirer & Kutan (2006) argue that herd formations do not exist in China's stock market. They used daily data for 375 companies from 1999 until 2002. According to the evidence presented in Table 2, however, China's stock market exhibits a different characteristic compared with the US market with respect to the herd effect.

6.2 State-ownership and Herd Effects

China's stock market exhibits significant herd behavior in both the entire market and different industries. The following test further investigates the relationship between herd behavior and state ownership in China's stock market. State-ownerships are commonly shown in both the Shanghai and Shenzhen stock markets. Especially for the initial few years (e.g., 1990-1993), there were considerable state-ownerships in China's stock market. As a process of China's economic reform, the state-owned company reform, in particular, plays a significant role in the changes of state-ownerships in the stock market. State ownership is constantly changing; however, it was especially prevalent in the early years of the stock market.

Since there were no private-owned companies when China's stock market initially started at the end of 1990, and only state-owned companies' stocks were traded in the market, ordinary individual investors held different points of view on stocks with regards to a stock's ownership structure even after two decades from the establishment of the stock market. In addition, the state-owned economy is still the largest proportion of China's economy and is still contributing significantly to China's economic growth. As a result, general individual investors prefer state-owned companies' stocks when they are facing the uncertainty of investment.

Therefore, there are sufficient grounds to hypothesize that different investing behavior based on state-ownerships among investors could be seen in stock return dispersions when the market is in extreme situations. To be more specific, when the market is either extremely low or extremely high, the market tends to herd around state-owned stocks. This is because when the market is experiencing price distress, more uncertainty is expected by investors. Therefore, unsophisticated investors should have less disagreement and more preference for stocks with a higher state-ownership proportion because these stocks are perceived to be safer than other comparable stocks. Consequently, stocks with a higher proportion of state-ownership should exhibit a lower dispersion of returns.

Table 3 Main Results

This table shows the regression results of two criteria of herding identification in both the 1% criterion and the 5% criterion. The dependent variables are dispersions in each distinct group. $D_t^U = 1$, if the market return on day t lies in the extreme upper tail of the return distribution, and $D_t^U = 0$ otherwise. The same logic applies to D_t^L . In order to group stocks with respect to state-ownership, we sort stocks in terms of the year-average state-ownerships into four diverse groups (group 0 (control) for companies with zero state-ownership; group 1(low) for companies with 0 to 25% state-ownership; group 2 (mid) for companies with 25% (included) to 50% state-ownership; group 3 (high) for companies with more than 50% (included) state-ownership). Group 0 is defined as the control group.

Group 1 is defined as the low-state-ownership group. Group 2 is defined as the mid-state-ownership group. Group 3 is defined as the high-state-ownership group.

	1 percent criterion			5 percent criterion		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(1)	(2)	(3)
D_t^L	-0.2350*** (-6.31)	-0.2351*** (-6.32)	-0.1856** (-2.57)	-0.3118*** (-19.51)	-0.3118*** (-19.52)	-0.2847*** (-9.17)
D_t^U	-0.5608*** (-14.54)	-0.5607*** (-14.54)	-0.4900*** (-6.53)	-0.6418*** (-40.16)	-0.6419*** (-40.19)	-0.6317*** (-20.36)
Group 3 (High)		-0.09279*** (-9.46)	-0.09036*** (-9.13)		-0.09275*** (-9.51)	-0.08660*** (-8.44)
Group 2 (Mid)		-0.1108*** (-11.51)	-0.1095*** (-11.28)		-0.1110*** (-11.60)	-0.1110*** (-11.03)
Group 1 (Low)		-0.09874*** (-10.33)	-0.09827*** (-10.19)		-0.09871*** (-10.39)	-0.09714*** (-9.72)
Group 0 (Control)		0	0		0	0
Dummy_L* Group 3 (High)			-0.2126** (-2.02)			-0.09561** (-2.11)
Dummy_L* Group 2 (Mid)			-0.05504 (-0.53)			0.01579 (0.35)
Dummy_L* Group 1 (Low)			0.05620 (0.54)			-0.03458 (-0.78)
Dummy_L* Group 0 (Control)			0			0
Dummy_U* Group 3 (High)			-0.07049 (-0.64)			-0.03096 (-0.68)
Dummy_U* Group 2 (Mid)			-0.09901 (-0.92)			-0.01460 (-0.33)
Dummy_U* Group 1 (Low)			-0.1164 (-1.09)			0.002220 (0.05)
Dummy_U* Group 0 (Control)			0			0
Industry Fixed Effect	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Group Fixed Effect	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
Intercept	3.5373	3.6115	3.6105	3.5770	3.6512	3.6494

To this end, the three regressions ((Equation 2, (Equation 3, and (Equation 4) are conducted and the results are shown in Table . It shows that the overall market exhibits herd behavior during both good and bad market states, and similarly, the herd effects during good market states (coefficients of D_t^U) are more than double the magnitude compared to bad market states (coefficients of D_t^L). As can be seen from column (2) of both the 1 percent criterion and 5 percent criterion, the coefficients of Group (High), Group (Mid) and Group (Low) are all significant at 1% level, indicating that the state-ownership is associated with herd behavior in China’s equity market.

It is worth mentioning that, after adding cross terms, the coefficients of indicators of state-ownerships (the four groups) are also significantly negative at 1% level, which suggests that the state-ownership is associated with herd behavior in China’s equity market. Notably, the coefficients of the cross-term *Dummy_L* Group (High)* of both the 1 percent criterion and 5 percent criterion are significantly negative

at 1% level, meaning that China's equity market herds around high state-ownerships when the market is extremely low. *Dummy_L* indicates market is under extremely low conditions. This might be the case that investors flock to state-owned companies to avoid their perceived risks. However, whether the preferences of investors for state-owned companies during bad markets provide investors with financial benefits is not yet clear.

Overall, the empirical tests provide strong evidence that China's equity market herds around state-owned companies. The herd effects in China's equity market are identified during both good and bad market states and among different industries, which indicates that herding is a market-wide feature and state-ownership is one of the reasons behind the herd effects.

7. Conclusion

The researcher documents significant confidence herding under market distress. Specifically, he shows that there is significant herding in the Chinese market during extreme market conditions (high/low), suggesting investor irrationality during such conditions. The magnitude of herding is greater (smaller) in extremely high (low) market conditions. Most importantly, he shows that investors exhibit significant herding in high-state-owned enterprises during extremely low market conditions, which might be the case that investors "flock" to high-state-owned enterprises for safety. This is because investors have a higher level of confidence in government ownership during extremely low market conditions. Though it is intuitive to suggest that investors tend to herd around state-owned stocks under market distress, future research should further explore micro-level evidence which demonstrates the decision-making process of investors under extreme market conditions. In contrast, investors do not exhibit significant herding in high-state-owned stocks during extremely high market conditions. Overall, the evidence has an important policy implication: government ownership introduces less market volatility during crises, in the sense that investors herd around government ownership with a lower level of dispersion of returns. This information is relevant to the policy makers in terms of the advancement of China's market-oriented economic reform. For instance, policy makers may have to consider the trade-off between the stock market stability associated with government ownership and the positive impacts of privatization of state-owned enterprises (Sun & Tong, 2003).

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